

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING STRATEGIES AIMED AT INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF RETAIL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Marketing strategies aimed at increasing the competitiveness of retail enterprises and directions for their development are researched in this scientific article.

Keywords: marketing strategy, competitiveness, competitive strategy, external environment, retail trade.

Introduction

Currently, much attention is paid to the strategic management of retail enterprises, because the rapid changes in the external environment force entrepreneurs to turn to new methods, systems and management approaches. In addition, the emergence of competitive companies such as Walmart, Amazon, Costco, Kroger, IKEA in the world retail market creates the need to develop marketing strategies aimed at increasing the competitiveness of retail enterprises. Therefore, the topic remains relevant to this day.

Strategy is a plan that integrates the main goals, policies, decisions and sequence of actions of the organization into a single whole. Strategy can be used at all levels of the organization and applies to any functional areas of management. Production, financial, marketing, personnel and corporate strategies can be expressed in this way. Marketing strategies include price, product, promotion, distribution, marketing research, sales, advertising, merchandising, and other areas of strategy development.

Strategy focuses more on efficiency than effectiveness and is a process of analyzing the environment and developing a fit between the organization, its resources and tasks, and the environment.

The strategic process refers to how the strategy is formulated.

There are several approaches:

first, a rational approach implemented through portfolio models of SWOT analysis and strategy analysis;

second, a flexible approach using multi-scenario planning;

creativity reflects the use of imagination in the planning process;

the behavioral approach reflects the influence of power, politics and individuals;

The incremental approach is based on small adjustments or changes to previously successful strategies [1].

Literature review

It should be noted that there are few economic concepts such as competitiveness, and there is much disagreement among academic economists in their interpretation. Analyzing several works related to the competitiveness of the enterprise and the product, we can say that there is no unity in the definition of the concept of "competitiveness".

Foreign experts in the field of economics and management interpret this economic term differently. Therefore, it is appropriate to study and summarize foreign and Russian approaches to defining the concept of "competitiveness" for a more detailed analysis. Initially A. The theory of competition generalized by Smith later D. Riccardo, F. Edgeworth, E. Chamberlin, G.L. Azoev, A. Yu. Yudanov and others. M. Porter, I. Ansoff, R. Waterman, A. Strickland, W.D. Andrianov, P.S. Zavialov, R.A. Fathutdinov studied not only the components of competition and competitiveness, but also the issues of ensuring competitiveness.

The selection of competitiveness as an independent economic category preceded the work of classical economists. Even A. Smith called free competition "the rule of the invisible hand", because according to the scientist, it directs the actions of people through their interests, determines the situation in the market, the success (ability) of all its participants, etc., thereby leading to the elimination of public problems that are most beneficial to both individuals and society as a whole [2].

In the interpretation of Yu.B. Ivanov, the competitiveness of the enterprise is the level of competence compared to other competing enterprises according to parameters such as technology, practical skills and knowledge of employees, level 9 of strategic and current planning, quality (management systems, production, products), communication. But the author does not take into account the competitive characteristics of the sold goods [3].

A.A. Radin considers the competitiveness of retail enterprises to be the ability of the enterprise not only to quickly respond to changes in the external and internal environment of a given market, but also to form changes in its potential needs and problems, foresee, and provide synergy. internal, external and logistics environment [4].

From the point of view of V.A. Moshnov, the competitiveness of a retail enterprise is its ability to create products sold on the market under conditions of free competition [5]. L.V. Tselikova defines the competitiveness of the enterprise in two components - market and resource: "Competitiveness of the enterprise is a complex economic description of the object of research in a certain market for a certain period of time, which reflects the level of its superiority. compared to its real competitors in two components - market and resource [6]. The most complete definitions of the competitiveness of the enterprise are given in the works of

N.S.Yashin, M.G.Dolinskaya and I.A.Solovyev. From the point of view of N.S. Yashin, the competitiveness of the enterprise is, on the one hand, a combination of the characteristics of the enterprise determined by the level of use of scientific, technical, production, personnel potential. marketing services performed in the process of reproduction, as well as, on the other hand, external socio-economic and organizational factors (legal basis of activity, financial and credit, tax policy; type and size of the market; characteristics of competitors); characteristics of the influence of public organizations and political parties, etc.) allow the enterprise to create products that are more attractive to consumers in terms of price and non-price characteristics than those of competitors [7].

M.H. Meskon, M. Albert and F. Khedouri divide the external environment of the company into two groups:

environment of direct influence (suppliers, consumers, competitors, trade unions, legislative and state bodies);

environment of indirect influence (economic situation, social and cultural factors, scientific and technical progress, international events).

The general effect of all factors of the environment forms its level of instability and thus forces the management of the company (enterprise) to develop adequate decisions aimed at the stable operation of the enterprise [8].

Analysis and results

In scientific literature, 4 types of marketing strategies are distinguished. These are:

- Main;
- Competitive;
- Global;
- Growth.

Among these, competitive strategy is the object of this study.

Figure 1. Types of competitive strategies

Competitive strategies depend on the situation in the company and the market. For example, Philip Kotler identifies four competitive strategies (Figure 1) [9]:

- Expansion

The company's market share is increasing due to investments. With this strategy, current income decreases as the company expands production: it builds new factories, hires employees, and buys equipment.

- hold

Despite the low growth rate, the company maintains its current position in the market due to its focus on promoting the products or services that generate the main income.

- harvest

Here and now profit maximization strategy is suitable for goods and services with an uncertain future. The company is betting on quick profits from their sales and, accordingly, rapid cost reductions until sales decline.

- reinvestment

Closing one line of business and reallocating resources to a new industry or developing a new product. This marketing strategy can be followed when the enterprise is liquidated or, for example, when the cost of producing a certain product reduces the company's profit.

Factors affecting marketing strategy in retail enterprises include:

- opening and closing strategic windows;
- influence of market factors;
- nature of competition in the market;
- market or industry life cycle stage;
- assets and skills that the firm has or can easily acquire / access [10].

Recognizing all of these five factors is essential if one is to develop effective long-term marketing strategies that lead to a sustainable strategy of competitive

advantage. One of the main important factors influencing marketing strategy today is competition.

Competition is important to influence the success of a company's business. A retail business must be able to position itself positively in the minds of its customers in order for its products and services to have an advantage over its competitors.

The nature and strength of competitors and how a firm competes for market position are key aspects of marketing and business strategy [11]. Technologies and products have lifecycles, as well as markets and industries. There are different stages in the life cycle of markets and industries that are important for marketing strategy.

Furthermore, given the number and strength of competitors in the market or at any given point in the life cycle, this creates a hard boundary within which a firm can develop an optimal marketing strategy.

It cannot be assumed that every firm can use the same situation to its advantage. Having or having access to the right skills and assets is critical to implementing successful marketing strategies. Without these assets and skills, a number of strategies may fail.

One of the best methods of strategic marketing is strategic windows. Abell (1978) introduced the concept of strategic window. The main idea of the strategic window concept is that there are only limited periods during which the compatibility between the main requirements of the market and the specific competencies of the firm competing in this market is acceptable. As a result, it is recommended that product line or market space investments coincide with strategic window periods.

The proposed argument is that as changes in the market and marketing environment increase, firms can successfully adapt to the new situation by changing current marketing and other functional tasks [12]. Such changes may occur as a result of technological innovations, changes in customer tastes, changes in legal regulations, economic and financial restrictions or any change in environmental conditions.

The nature of competition may also change, particularly the five elements of Porter's (1980) model of competition. These are:

- New participants may appear in the market;

- Updated products can become more attractive offers to customers;

- both suppliers and buyers can define their bargaining power as the strongest;

- with the development of competitive advantages of one of the firms, the balance of power in the competition between existing firms in the market may change [13].

However, if the cumulative changes in the economic, technological, social, political and cultural environment are not taken into account by company managers until it is too late to react, the problems they create for the firm can be very difficult to overcome.

Similarly, when the degree of market volatility reaches such a level that the firm's ability to continue to compete effectively is called into question, the firm may face the closing of an important strategic window.

If changes are made too quickly or too slowly, ultimately closing the policy window, the consequences can be disastrous.

In the first case, the window closes before the organization reacts, in the second case, the window is not noticed until it is too late to understand and react.

It is important to consider not only where the firm is now, but also how well equipped it is to deal with tomorrow. In particular, the task of predicting non-cumulative changes in the market is crucial.

Developing a marketing strategy is an ongoing process. If you do research, write a strategy and do not change anything for several years, there is a risk of not achieving your goals and serious losses.

Marketing strategy can be divided into four main stages:

Stage 1. Data analysis.

At this stage of strategy development, market, competitor, audience, product and advertising channel research is conducted.

Step 2. Marketing strategy planning.

Based on the analysis, goals and tasks are determined, resources are evaluated and priorities are selected. Before moving on to the next level, you will need to improve the product, reposition the brand, or hire additional professionals.

Step 3. Implementation of marketing strategy.

At this stage, advertising campaigns are developed and launched on selected advertising channels. Timelines, budgets, and performance evaluation methods are defined in the marketing strategy plan.

Step 4. Interim control of results.

In addition to controlling deadlines and budgets, at this stage of marketing strategy development, you need to account for each event and analyze the reasons for success and failure. It will help you to monitor changes in the market in time, find errors in planning and expand successful tactics.

The stages of developing a marketing strategy are cyclical. After the control phase, the strategy can be refined or revised based on the results.

Conclusions and suggestions

When developing competitive marketing strategies and creating marketing plans in retail enterprises, first of all, it is necessary to check the goals set for the quarter, year, and five years. Then you need to plan what combination of channels and tools will lead to the achievement of these goals.

Often, marketing leaders focus on the tools and channels they are experts in, such as performance marketing. Creating a balanced marketing strategy requires an understanding of other areas.

At different stages of competitive advantage marketing strategies, each element of integrated marketing has a different priority. Therefore, it is important to regularly evaluate whether the chosen tools are suitable for the current stage and goals, whether KPIs are chosen correctly to measure the effectiveness of each tool.

Thus, it is possible to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise by creating a more effective marketing strategy using more complete consideration and analysis of the factors related to the operation and development of the market.

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